

CONCEPTS OF LEADERSHIP PERSONALITY AND MANAGEMENT CULTURE**Qobilov Husniddin Norqo'chqor o'gli****Ergasheva Izzat Toshtemirovna****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7058085>**

Abstract: Management culture is the rules and norms formally and informally introduced by management to lead the organization towards its goals. We can observe management culture in the management of society and management of organizations and institutions.

Key words: management culture, goal, social activity, method, social process.

ПОНЯТИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ ЛИДЕРА И КУЛЬТУРЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация: Культура управления – это правила и нормы, формально и неформально внедряемые руководством, чтобы вести организацию к достижению ее целей. Мы можем наблюдать культуру управления в управлении обществом и управлении организациями и учреждениями.

Ключевые слова: культура управления, цель, социальная деятельность, метод, социальный процесс.

INTRODUCTION

Analyzing from this point of view, management culture can be described as a set of activities aimed at further accelerating human resources in order to achieve the goal. In its essence, the management culture performs the function of coordinating the activities of all departments participating in the organization's activities and carrying out educational work at the organization level.

According to psychologist E. Gozиеv, "one of the universal, necessary qualities for any leader is to be "intellectual" in the literal sense, or in other words, to be cultured."

"We need to know that leadership is not a job, but a responsibility to serve people. A leader should be a selfless person who works more than anyone else, who strives for the happiness of citizens and the development of the country, - says the First President of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov - the people always evaluate the work of leaders based on their table, lifestyle. There should not be leaders who tarnish the honor of defense with their actions."

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Management culture is the implementation of management taking into account the motivations of employees and their values. In the process of such management, the selection and use of various tools becomes an urgent issue. Management culture is a phenomenon that expresses the essence of personnel management. A rationally organized management culture

creates great opportunities to accelerate the existing human resources in the organization and thereby further increase work efficiency. By perfecting the management culture, it directs the production of such factors as the hidden capabilities of the company's personnel - knowledge, experience, creative potential, employees' desire to express themselves, and motivations. The current management culture is also reflected in the organizational culture formed at the scale of this enterprise. In this sense, by perfecting the management culture, it is possible to form leading values, standards of behavior, interaction between employees and attitude to work in the organization.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The introduction of the concept of management culture into management science implies a number of theoretical and practical innovations. Until now, the term management mainly refers to the management position, laws and regulations related to management, but now the values, mental capabilities, and expectations of employees, which are characteristic of a person, have also become the object of management. Taking into account these additional factors made it possible to turn the management of the organization into a somewhat integrated, whole and systematic process.

As the development of the society rises to new levels of development, the management culture is perfected in accordance with the requirements of the time. In the current era of rapid development, the viability of the enterprise is determined by the production of competitive products that can meet the demands of the times. In such conditions, the management culture of the organization should be aimed at introducing innovative projects as much as possible.

Management culture is the essence of the mutual trust relationship between the administration and employees at the organization level, and the government and citizens at the community level. In such conditions, it is necessary to change and improve the management culture not only in content, but also in form. In particular, in the current development of the society, the management culture is increasingly absorbing democratic principles.

Management culture within the organization is manifested in the following types of management attitudes:

- attitude towards the person;
- operating technologies in the existing enterprise;
- time spent on production;
- In planning the enterprise's activities;
- Methods of achieving the organization's goal;

- Methods of incentives and punishments applied to employees;
- On the characteristics of employee growth at the enterprise level.

Management culture can be described as a form of culture in this society. In this respect, the management culture in a specific organization and institution reflects the main aspects of the culture practiced in the state administration. When developing the main principles of management culture, it is necessary to take into account the main factors determining the culture of this society, and especially national characteristics. The task of mutual coordination of economic, social and political goals arises in the improvement of management at the organization level, and further improvement of human resources management. Such a need is the main condition for the development of the enterprise. Management culture is a process of continuous application of existing knowledge as a form of social control. This process is constantly developing and perfecting, and should reflect the latest innovations and discoveries of science. Subjects implementing management culture are, first of all, leaders. Therefore, raising their scientific and cultural potential is the most urgent issue in training modern leaders.

DISCUSSION

When it comes to the management of the social sphere of society, the management culture here has its own characteristics, different from the management of the organization. The traditional management methods specific to this society have a certain historical content and embody the mentality, values, inner intentions and traditions of the citizens of the society. Currently, there are 2 main management cultures in society management, one of them is authoritarian and the other is democratic management. The culture of authoritarian rule is manifested in the state policy based on a single ideology, and is expressed in the dictatorship of one class. It is known from history that the dictatorship of the "proletariat", which ruled in the former colonial system, is a clear example of this. Currently, Uzbekistan is based on the principles of democratic governance in the management of society on the way to building a legal state.

CONCLUSION

From the stated cases, it can be concluded that in any quality management, it is time to put content before form, to pay more attention to the life of the organization, in particular, to the mood and morale of employees. Research conducted by sociologists on the example of banks operating in Uzbekistan shows that one of the main reasons why a client depends on a bank and does not switch from one bank to another is the culture of interaction with the client. Such an emphasis can be interpreted in the example of any service organization.

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